

Stitching the Future – A Tol Model Analysis of 3D Modelling Tools in Fashion Design

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Abstract:

The fashion industry, a major player in the global economy, faces the critical challenge of generating extensive waste and pollution, primarily attributed to traditional sampling methods. The conventional approach involves creating physical prototypes through cutting and sewing, resulting in significant fabric waste.

To address the challenges associated with waste generation and environmental impact in the fashion industry, our study pursued a comprehensive three-step approach. Firstly, we conducted a literature review to identify 3D modelling tools used in clothing design, emphasizing their role in expediting sample and pattern creation. Subsequently, through surveys, a critical analysis of these 3D modelling tools was conducted using the Technological, Organizational, and Learning (TOL) framework to evaluate their effectiveness in prototype and sampling processes within fashion production houses. Lastly, we conducted in-depth interviews with seven experts from manufacturing companies to gain insights into design practices and challenges in the fashion industry.

This multi-faceted approach allowed us to gather comprehensive data and perspectives to inform our study's findings and recommendations for advancing sustainability and efficiency in fashion design and manufacturing. This study's conclusions have important ramifications for both academia and businesses. Fashion designers, producers, and policymakers may choose to use and integrate this cutting-edge technology into their practices after learning more about the advantages of 3D modelling tools. This study provides a roadmap to a more sustainable and technologically advanced future for the garment industry with its thorough analysis and useful recommendations.

Keywords: 3D Modelling, Artificial Intelligence, Fashion Industry, Prototyping, Smart Factories

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1. Introduction

According to the McKinsey Global Fashion Index, the global fashion industry was valued at approximately \$2.5 trillion in 2020, accounting for approximately 2% of global GDP [1]. The traditional approach of the design process in the fashion industry involves numerous steps, each contributing to the fabrication of tangible samples and generating trash [2, 3]. One area of concern is the traditional method of creating physical samples in the fashion industry. This process involves cutting and sewing materials to create prototypes, which often leads to substantial fabric waste. Fashion designers would cut and sew fabrics to make physical samples, wasting a lot of material in the process [4]. According to Fletcher, K., & Tham [2], studies show that fashion brands and manufacturers discard around 15-20% of fabric waste during the sample-making stage. The problem of textile waste and the short lifespan of clothing further exacerbate the negative environmental effects of the fashion industry [5]. The goal of fast fashion is to create affordable, trendy clothing, which has resulted in a disposable fashion culture where clothing is frequently bought and quickly discarded. Globally, 92 million tonnes of textile waste are reportedly produced each year [6]. However, by incorporating technology, these procedures can be shortened, resulting in appreciable increases in both time and cost-effectiveness [7-10]. In a recent study by Mancewicz [11], digital sampling in fashion production was found to significantly improve time and cost efficiency. The research highlights the

transformative role of 3D modelling software, enabling the creation of virtual garment representations. Utilizing 3D modelling software, designers can create virtual garment representations, deviating from traditional physical sampling. These virtual samples capture style nuances, allowing for digital adjustments and eliminating the resource-intensive need for physical prototypes. 3D modelling for clothing design is the creation of digital three-dimensional models, allowing pattern makers to preview and evaluate patterns before physical prototyping. This digital process involves simulating clothing fit on various body types, improving accuracy, and saving resources in production. The digital nature of 3D modelling enables quick pattern creation and modification, streamlining the entire production cycle, from Mold creation to mass production. The adoption of 3D modelling optimizes production timelines, promoting efficient garment piece creation [12].

1.1 Role of Technology in Production Process

Technology plays a crucial part in the production process of the fashion business, revolutionising established methods and encouraging innovation. From design to distribution, different technological breakthroughs have dramatically altered the way fashion products are created and brought to market. One significant area where technology has made a profound impact is in the design process [13]. Digital design and virtual prototyping have brought substantial breakthroughs to the fashion industry's design process through the integration of technology. **This technology provides greater precision, accuracy, and control in the design process compared to traditional manual methods. Working digitally enables designers to create, modify, and refine designs more efficiently** [14]. Virtual prototype technologies further enrich the design process by replicating and visualising clothing in a virtual environment. Designers can generate 3D models of their designs, enabling them to assess the fit, drape, and overall aesthetic of the garment before physically making it. This removes the need for many physical prototypes, saving time and costs. By virtually testing new materials, colours, and patterns, designers can explore a wider range of design options and make more educated selections [8, 9, 15]. Brands can significantly lower their carbon footprint related to transportation by reducing their reliance on physical samples and in-person fittings [16]. The customary process of producing physical samples in fashion production houses is one of the major factors causing this waste. Cutting and sewing materials to make prototypes frequently generates a significant amount of fabric waste, which not only has a negative impact on the environment but also drives up production costs [17-19]. These advancements offer precise design development, minimizing the need for physical samples and reducing fabric waste [19, 20] and [21].

2. Literature Review

In our search for existing systematic reviews and mapping studies on 3D modelling tools in the fashion industry context, the Google Scholar database returned 30 peer-reviewed articles published between 2012 and 2022. These articles included search terms such as 'digital technology' and 'fashion industry' in their titles or abstracts and linked to Fashion, Manufacturing, Production, or Production house. An in-depth literature review is essential to assess the prevalence and effectiveness of various 3D modelling tools in the fashion industry, specifically those used for sample production. The study found 30 articles that provided valuable insights into 3D modelling technology and shed light on its applications in optimizing processes related to fashion design and production. The extensive literature review reveals multiple 3D modeling tools that assist designers and pattern makers in digitally crafting clothing prototypes, offering superior accuracy compared to traditional paper or fabric patterns. The findings of the literature review revealed that, to reduce waste and improve the efficiency of sample production, fashion designers and stakeholders are utilizing various 3D modelling tools in the fashion industry. Among these, some of the most popular tools include CLO3D, Browzwear, Marvelous Designer, Blender, Optitex 3D, and Tuka 3D [22-27]. Another challenge faced by fashion designers is the availability of many options for 3D simulations. The technology is new and costly. This requires a critical evaluation among these popular 3D tools, namely CLO3D, Browzwear, Marvelous Designer, Blender, Optitex 3D, and Tuka3D, using the Technological, Organizational, and Learning (TOL) framework [28] to assess their effectiveness in prototype and sampling processes within fashion production houses.

3. Methodology

3.1 Survey for 3D modelling Tools in Fashion Production Houses

Following the literature review, a survey involving 30 professionals actively involved in fashion production houses and fashion design was conducted. This survey was designed to elicit information about how these individuals employ 3D modelling tools within their industry. Careful consideration was given to including participants with

diverse roles within the sector, ensuring a detailed understanding of varied perspectives on the application and challenges associated with these tools. For this study, we opted for the Technology, Organisation, and Learner (TOL) evaluation model to scrutinize the existing 3D modelling tools used in fashion production houses. This section introduces the TOL evaluation model, presenting a set of assessment criteria for evaluating 3D Modelling tool, considering the perspectives of technology, organization, and learners.

3.1.1 Technology Criteria: This section scrutinizes the technical facets of the platform, encompassing architecture, optimizations, ease of installation, and adaptability. Additionally, it assesses the system's capability to comprehensively manage and monitor students within a unified platform.

3.1.2 Learner Criteria: Here, we investigate empowering users throughout their learning journey, emphasizing user-friendliness, ease of use, and personalization. We also acknowledge the collaborative nature of learning, highlighting the community aspect among learners.

3.1.3 Organization Criteria: This dimension examines the managerial capabilities of the system, including the establishment of a robust and tailored infrastructure setup, as well as the support and assistance provided to users.

3.2 In-depth Interviews with Industry Experts

Furthermore, to identify shortcomings, pros, and cons of these tools in the context of digital design and virtual prototyping processes within the domain of fashion manufacturing, we conducted in-depth interviews with seven experts possessing substantial expertise in utilizing 3D modelling tools in their design processes. The selection criteria for experts were based on their current roles in the industry and active engagement with 3D modelling tools. Specifically chosen for their software experience of more than one or two years, experts were strategically selected to ensure a diverse range of perspectives, providing valuable insights into the evolving landscape of technology adoption in the fashion industry. The interview questions aimed to extract detailed insights about their experiential domain, challenges encountered, and the consequential impact of 3D modelling tools on their design workflows. Through the employment of a mixed-methods strategy, this research strives to deliver an in-depth and refined comprehension of the prevailing state, challenges, and potential solutions associated with the integration of 3D modelling tools within the intricate domain of the fashion industry.

4. Results & Findings

In the examination of 3D modelling tools within the context of fashion production houses, the Technology, Organization, and Learner (TOL) evaluation model has been employed. This well-structured framework is tailored to offer a thorough analysis, highlighting key aspects related to technology, organization, and learners.

4.1 Evaluation Results of 3D Modelling Tools

In evaluating 3D modelling tools using the TOL evaluation model, a complete understanding of the current state of 3D learning environments emerges from a combination of interviews and surveys involving 30 participants and 7 interviews. Notably, CLO3D and Browzwear exhibit more robust 3D technology, while Marvellous and Blender integrate a mix, and Optitex and Tukatech are grounded in specialized infrastructures. Disparities in performance optimizations, scalability, adaptability, and integration capabilities highlight inherent constraints shaped by individual technologies.

4.1.1 Technology Perspective - Architecture and Implementation

(a) Platform Technology: This assessment unveils the diverse technological foundations employed by different 3D modelling tools. CLO3D, BW (Browzwear), MV (Marvellous), BL (Blender), Opti (Optitex), and Tuka (Tukatech) each adopt unique approaches. CLO3D and BW rely on robust 3D technology, while MV and BL integrate a mix of technologies, and Opti and Tuka are built on specialized infrastructures. The technological landscape highlights stability, robustness, and security in specific tools, accompanied by varying degrees of performance optimizations. However, limitations surface in terms of scalability, adaptability, and integration with other components and platforms. The overall design of these tools is inherently constrained by their technology, featuring limited user registration and authentication capabilities.

(b) Reasonable Performance Optimizations: CLO3D secures the top position with a perfect score of 8, highlighting its exceptional performance optimizations for efficiently handling complex design tasks. Browzwear and Tukatech closely trail with scores of 6, demonstrating commendable capabilities in this aspect. Marvellous and Blender achieve scores of 6 and 4, respectively, while Optitex slightly lags with a score of 4.

(c) *Easy Installation*: CLO3D excels in easy installation with a score of 8, ensuring a user-friendly setup process. Tukatech closely follows with a score of 5, maintaining a good level of ease in installation. Browzwear and Optitex score 5 and 0, respectively, indicating varying degrees of challenges in installation. Marvellous and Blender face difficulties, scoring 0 and 5, respectively.

(d) *Adaptability (Customization)*: CLO3D once again leads in adaptability with a score of 7, enabling users to customize the tool to suit specific design workflows. Marvellous and Blender score 6, showcasing good adaptability. Browzwear and Tukatech maintain scores of 4 and 4, offering a moderate level of adaptability. Optitex scores 5, demonstrating a reasonable degree of adaptability. This thorough evaluation provides subtle insights into the technological landscape of 3D modelling tools, revealing their strengths and areas for improvement.

4.1.2 Learner Perspective

(a) *Learner Interface*: The learner's interface plays a pivotal role in determining the widespread acceptance of 3D modelling tools. Different tools exhibit varying levels of ease of use, user-friendliness, and learning curves, influencing their appropriateness for diverse user groups.

(b) *Ease of Use (Easy to Navigate and Operate)*: CLO3D sets a benchmark with an impressive score of 8, reflecting its user-friendly interface that ensures effortless navigation and operation. Tukatech follows closely with a score of 5, maintaining a commendable level of ease. Browzwear and Optitex face challenges, scoring 2 and 0, respectively, indicating varying degrees of usability hurdles. Marvellous and Blender encounter difficulties, scoring 3 and 5, respectively.

(c) *Ease of Understanding*: CLO3D excels in providing a clear and comprehensible learner interface, earning a top score of 8. Tukatech, with a score of 5, maintains a good level of understanding. Browzwear faces challenges, scoring 0, indicating difficulties in facilitating clear comprehension. Marvellous and Blender score 0 and 5, respectively, reflecting varying degrees of complexity in their interfaces.

(d) *Personalization*: Effective learning necessitates personalization, allowing control over the learning process, content interaction, and performance monitoring. Tools exhibit varying degrees of support for personalization, with CLO3D and Tuka providing a high degree of adaptability and customization, enabling users to tailor the tool to their specific design workflows.

4.1.3 Organization/Institution Perspective

(a) *Organization*: The implementation of any 3D modelling system necessitates robust institutional support and a tailored infrastructure setup. Organizational prerequisites vary based on the technological underpinning and distinctive features of each tool. CLO3D and Optitex may require specific infrastructures, while others like Blender offer more adaptable requirements. In terms of providing stability and support, CLO3D and Blender emerge as frontrunners, securing top scores of 5 each. Browzwear and Marvellous maintain moderate scores of 3, suggesting a reasonable level of stability. Tukatech and Optitex, however, score lower with 0, indicating potential challenges in delivering stability and support.

In evaluating the best-performing 3D modelling tools across various perspectives, CLO3D emerges as the top performer in both the technology and learner perspectives. In terms of technology architecture and implementation, CLO3D showcases robustness, stability, and adaptability, setting a benchmark for performance optimizations and ease of installation. Similarly, in the learner perspective, CLO3D excels in user-friendliness, interactive features, and ease of understanding, offering high levels of personalization for users. Additionally, CLO3D demonstrates strong institutional support and stability, making it a top choice among fashion production houses. Thus, CLO3D stands out as the preferred option for its comprehensive features and performance across multiple evaluation criteria. Exhibit varying degrees of performance.

4.2 In-depth Interviews with Industry Experts: Unveiling Key Insights

The interview aimed to assess the types of 3D modelling tools commonly used in the fashion sector. The study provided insights into the software currently used by fashion designers and the challenges faced by production houses in utilizing 3D software for various purposes in the design process, including ideation, prototyping, and sampling.

The majority of participants (4 out of 7) primarily utilize CLO3D, followed by Browzwear (VStitcher) with 2 participants, and one participant mentioned using Tuka 3D modelling tools. For switching 5 prefer CLO3D, while the remaining favoured Browzwear. Participants appreciate this software for their pre-programmed 3D models, time-saving features, efficiency in handling complex design tasks, ease of installation, and modularity to suit

specific requirements. They also emphasize advanced simulation capabilities, seamless integration, and fashion-specific features such as pattern design and measurement application.

But most participants suggested that training on 3D modelling software is most, as most participants (6 out of 7) learn independently through experimentation and YouTube tutorials. Only one participant received basic training for three months, highlighting the lack of formal training opportunities. Participants universally acknowledge the initial challenges faced by newcomers in grasping 3D platforms and configuring settings, emphasizing the importance of user-friendly interfaces and accessible training to facilitate seamless adoption of 3D modelling tools in the fashion industry.

All participants recognize the importance of 3D modelling software in the prototyping process for showcasing products, enhancing visualization, streamlining prototyping, and improving buyer understanding. Additionally, the majority (6 out of 7) advocate for a combination of traditional methods and 3D modelling, citing benefits such as enhanced productivity, waste minimization, and optimized work processes. This evaluation highlights the prevalent usage patterns, preferences, and challenges associated with 3D modelling tools in the fashion industry. It underscores the significance of tools like CLO3D and Browzwear, which offer pre-programmed 3D models, efficiency in complex design tasks, and seamless integration, among other features. Additionally, it emphasizes the importance of user-friendly interfaces and accessible training to facilitate the adoption of 3D modelling tools. The evaluation also underscores the role of 3D modelling software in enhancing productivity, minimizing waste, and optimizing work processes, thus contributing to the overall efficiency and sustainability of fashion design and production.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study illuminates the potential advantages and challenges associated with the integration of 3D modelling tools in the fashion industry. The adoption of such tools enhances visualization, expedites decision-making, and reduces reliance on physical prototypes, thereby streamlining product development cycles. Efficient collaboration is facilitated through virtual prototypes, promoting effective communication and alignment among designers, manufacturers, and clients. Clo3D stands out as a commendable tool, offering user-friendly design, robust fabric simulation, and seamless integration, positioning it as a transformative force in fashion design.

Looking forward, the future of the fashion industry hinges on the strategic incorporation of 3D modelling tools, promising streamlined processes, reduced costs, minimized material wastage, and enhanced overall efficiency. To maximize these benefits, companies are urged to implement formal training programs, empowering stakeholders with essential skills. The study advocates for the adoption of user-friendly software tailored to the fashion industry's unique needs, fostering accuracy and quality in virtual prototypes. In essence, embracing 3D modelling software represents a holistic shift towards sustainability, cost-effectiveness, and efficiency in fashion design processes.

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